

Tunneling Fundamentals, Practice and Innovations Annual Short Course

Special Session on University Transportation Infrastructure

October 17, 2019

Stochastic Analysis of Thermal Demand and Resulting Capacity Loss of Concrete Tunnel Liners Subjected to Vehicle Fires

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Tunnel Safety

(USDOT & FHWA, 2015)

Seven recently completed European projects on tunnel safety (NCHRP Synthesis 415)

Project	Logo	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006
FIT		Consultable Databases & Guidelines					
DARTS		Cost-optimal & durable new design					
Safe Tunnel		Preventive safety measures					
Sirtaki		Advanced tunnel management					
Virtual Fires		Tunnel fire simulator					
UPTUN		Upgrading of existing tunnels - Innovation					
SafeT ?		Harmonised European Guidelines					

Accumulated tunnel inventory from 1882 to 2015 (USDOT & FHWA, 2015)

A Tesla sits at an entrance to the Boring Company's test tunnel. (Dec. 2018, CNN)

Tunnel Fire Safety

Vehicle Fire Demand Evaluation

Prescribed Design

Numerical Analysis

RWS Fire Curve

- Obtained experimentally from **one** severe fire scenario in **one** tunnel **at the worst location** to achieve a conservative design

High Fidelity Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) Software

- Computational inefficient
- Large amounts of input

Uncertainties of Fire Hazard in Tunnels

- **Fire Frequency**
 - Length of the tunnel
 - Traffic data of the tunnel
- **Fire Size**
 - Vehicle size (car, bus, heavy goods vehicle, etc.)
 - Materials on the vehicle (wood, fuel, plastic, etc.)
- **Heat Exposure**
 - Tunnel geometry
 - Ventilation system
 - Fire fighting system
- **Tunnel Damage**
 - Material types
 - Material properties
- ...

Stochastic Analysis of Vehicle Fire Hazard in Tunnels

Fire Frequency
Fire Severity

Latin Hypercube
Sampling Method

A Sample of Fire
Sizes (HRR)

Fire Model: Confined Discretized
Solid Flame (CDSF) Model

Heat Flux on Tunnel
Liners

Heat Transfer
Analysis

Concrete Liner
Strength Reduction

Frequency Distribution of HRR

Fire Frequency

- Fire rate definition: per million vehicle-km
- Statistical average fire rate from D.A.R.T.S report
 - 45 tunnels from 13 countries in Europe
- Weighted fire rate for different vehicle types
 - HGV fire rate is almost twice that for car fires
- Fire frequency of a vehicle type per period
= (Fire rate of the vehicle type) × (Vehicle Traffic in a period) × (Tunnel length)
- Fire rate of the vehicle type
= (Average fire rate) × (Weight of the vehicle type)
- For example,...
- Fire frequency of HGV per year
= (0.041 × 1.6) × (HGV Traffic per year) × (Tunnel length in km)

Fire Severity and Fire Sample Generation

- Sample Size and proportions
- Latin Hypercube Sampling
 - Stratified into uniform layers
 - Random in each layer
 - More efficient compared to Monte Carlo Simulation

Vehicle Types	Peak HRR (MW)	Distribution	Mean	Standard Deviation	Relative Factor	Weighted Fire Rate (per mil. veh-km)
Motorcycle	1-5	Normal	3	2	0.6	0.025
Car	5-10	Normal	7.5	2.5	0.8	0.033
Pickup/Van	10-20	Normal	15	5	1.2	0.049
Bus	20-30	Normal	25	5	1.2	0.049
HGV	30-200	Normal	115	85	1.6	0.066

Heat Exposure Evaluation – CDSF Model

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- **Radiation:**

- Discretized solid flame with surface emissive power
- Tunnel confinement taken into account
- Target heat flux determined by the emissive power and view factor of emitting surface of the flame

- **Convection:**

- Convective region depth
- Maximum convective heat flux
- Longitudinal decay from the maximum
- Transverse decay from the maximum
- Natural ventilation is assumed

Heat Exposure Evaluation – CDSF Model

Heat Transfer in the Concrete and Corresponding Strength Reduction

Heat Transfer in the Concrete

- Concrete panel with heat flux time history applied on one surface
- Thru-thickness heat transfer analysis with SAFIR (FEM Software)
- Produce temperature time history in each element layer

Concrete Strength Reduction during heating and after cooling down

- Maximum temperature of the time history in each layer is used for the reduced strength calculation

Case Study: Fort Pitt Tunnel (Pittsburgh, PA)

- Opened in 1960
- Horseshoe-shaped cross-section with 2 bores
- Length: 1102 m
- Width: 8.94m
- Maximum height: 6.58m

Vehicle Types	Peak HRR (MW)	Weighted Fire Rate	Avg. Daily Traffic in 2019	%Total Traffic in 2019	Fire Frequency per Year	% Total Fire Frequency per Year
Motorcycle	1-5	0.025	363	0.4%	0.004	0.23%
Car	5-10	0.033	81799	79.1%	1.102	69.64%
Pickup/Van	10-20	0.049	13455	13.0%	0.272	17.18%
Bus	20-30	0.049	1024	1.0%	0.021	1.31%
HGV	30-200	0.066	6832	6.6%	0.184	11.63%
Totals:			103473	100%	1.582	100%

Case Study: Sample Generating

Case Study: Results and Application

Case Study: Results and Application

Conclusion

- A probabilistic framework can be used to assess the expected amount of fire related damage to tunnel infrastructure.
- The Fort Pitt Tunnel has a calculated fire frequency per year of about 1.53 fire/year, in which passenger car fires are the biggest segment (70%).
 - Given that a vehicle fire occurs, there is 88% of probability that the HRR is lower than 25MW.
- Two heat flux milestones (60 kW/m^2 and 560 kW/m^2) are selected where the cumulative frequency reaches 86.1% and 99.9%, between which the curve is almost flat .
- Thru-thickness concrete compressive strength loss can be used as a means for decision making about fire protection design, renovation, and post-fire inspection for tunnels.
- Future work will develop case studies for tunnel infrastructure.

Acknowledgement(s)

- Support from the University Transportation Center for Underground Transportation Infrastructure (UTC-UTI) at the Colorado School of Mines for funding this research under Grant No. 69A3551747118 from the U.S. Department of Transportation (DOT) is gratefully acknowledged.